

Music Therapy in Hospital Settings : From the Perspective of a Medical Music Therapist

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Abstract

Elements of music are consolidated in vocal and or instrumental forms to express numerous types of emotions. The brain, body, and music are inextricably linked. As a result of this relationship, music can have an impact on an individual's physiological and psychological well-being. Music's incredible journey from music healing to music therapy in hospital settings as an interdisciplinary approach took thousands of years. In this review article, we discuss the incredible history of music, the description of music therapy, the distinction between music therapy, music medicine, and music as performance, the effect of music on the brain and behavior, the neural processes underlying physiological and psychological changes caused by music, music therapy as a non-pharmacological treatment module and scientific evidence to support music therapy for patient care in different areas of the hospital.

সারসংক্ষেপ

মানুষের বিভিন্ন ধরনের আবেগ আছে এবং সংগীতের নানা উপাদানগুলো কণ্ঠ এবং যন্ত্রের দ্বারা সে সকল আবেগ বা অনুভূতিকে প্রকাশ করতে সাহায্য করে। মস্তিষ্ক, শরীর ও সংগীত অঙ্গঙ্গীভাবে জড়িত, এ সম্পর্কের ফলশ্রুতিতে সংগীত একজন ব্যক্তির শারীরিক ও মানসিক সুস্থতার ওপর অনেক প্রভাব বিস্তার করতে পারে। হাজার বছর পূর্ব থেকেই চিকিৎসকরা সংগীতের এ নিরাময় ক্ষমতা সম্পর্কে অবগত ছিল এবং তারা সংগীতকে চিকিৎসা হিসেবে ব্যবহার করতো। প্রাচীনকালের সংগীত চিকিৎসা থেকে শুরু করে হাসপাতালের সেটিংসে মিউজিক থেরাপির একটি আন্তঃবিভাগীয় পদ্ধতি হিসেবে যুক্ত হতে এ অবিশ্বাস্যকর যাত্রায় লেগে গেছে হাজার হাজার বছর। এই পর্যালোচনা নিবন্ধে, আমরা সংগীতের অবিশ্বাস্য ইতিহাস; মিউজিক থেরাপির বর্ণনা; মিউজিক থেরাপি, মিউজিক মেডিসিন এবং পরিবেশনা হিসেবে সংগীতের পার্থক্য; মানুষের মস্তিষ্ক এবং আচরণের উপর সংগীতের প্রভাব; সংগীতের প্রভাবে সৃষ্ট শারীরবৃত্তীয় ও মনস্তাত্ত্বিক পরিবর্তনের অন্তর্নিহিত নিউরাল প্রক্রিয়াগুলো নিয়ে আলোচনা ; নন- ফার্মাকোলজিক্যাল চিকিৎসা মডিউল হিসেবে মিউজিক থেরাপি এবং হাসপাতালের বিভিন্ন বিভাগে রোগীর যত্নের জন্য মিউজিক থেরাপির গুরুত্ব প্রমাণের জন্য বৈজ্ঞানিক নানা গবেষণার প্রমাণ তুলে ধরা হয়েছে।

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“One good thing about music, when it hits you, you feel no pain.”- Bob Marley

From birds chirping and waves lapping against a coastline to cars honking in traffic, sounds surround us. Co-ordinated sound or sounds make up music. The music derives from vibrations, and vibrations exist throughout the universe and earth. Pythagoreans believed that earthly music was developed from the music of spheres which is the microcosmic reflection of macrocosmic order.¹

Are all of the sounds music? For calling it music, the sounds need to have some qualities. The complete package of music comes from rhythm, lyrics, melody and dynamics (harmony in western music).² Music was the medium of communication from the ancient period of human development. Around 35,000 years ago when even language was not developed that time our ancestors used to play bone flutes to alert other members of the clan about the danger.³ Music was also used as a healing power in many cultures by shamans. Even Pythagoras and Plato were aware of the curative power of music and that’s why they believed that music connects the mind-body-spiritual aspect of a human being.¹ In the Indian sub-continent, it is believed that the sound and vibration of “AUM” chanting has been extracted from the vibration of the universe, which is the keystone of Shabda-Brahm and Nada Brahm.⁴

Music therapy is the composition of music and medicine. It is a branch of interdisciplinary medicine where certified music therapists work in hospitals, rehabilitation centers, educational areas etc. Various organizations and music therapists have tried to define music therapy through their learning and experiences. In 2011, world federation of music therapy (WFMT) briefed that,

“Music therapy is the professional use of music and its elements as an intervention in medical, educational and everyday environments with individuals, groups, families or communities who seek to optimize their quality of life and improve their physical, social, communicative, emotional, intellectual and spiritual health and well-being. Research, practice, education and clinical training in music therapy are based on professional standards according to cultural, social, and political contexts.”⁵

Music therapy is a clinical and evidence-based health profession that is conducted by a certified music therapist, wherein the therapist creates a therapeutic relationship with the client and uses musical experience to address the physical, emotional, cognitive and social needs of an individual or a group.^{6,7,8} As a part of music therapy, pre-recorded music listening whenever is used by a music therapist with a therapeutic relationship is called music therapy. Without a music therapist and a therapeutic relationship whenever pre-recorded music is used by other medical health professionals such as doctors, nurses and therapists for the improvement of the patients that is termed as music medicine.⁹ Except the professional music therapists, the use of music for physiological and or psychological issues are not considered as music therapy.⁸

Medical music therapists follow the bio-psychosocial approach where they keep the patients

biological, psychological and social factors into consideration. Music therapists believe that an individual's illness or well-being can be properly treated by analyzing all of these factors.¹⁰

Music therapy connects to mind, body, brain and behavior. It helps to bring changes in an individual's physical, psychological and behavioral level. Slow-beat music makes our heartbeats, blood pressure, breathing slowly and we feel relaxed. At the same time, fast-beat music makes the heart rate faster.^{11,12} Now the question arises why and how it happens? How music affects our body? How it's helping for the physical and psychological betterment of the patient?

Music doesn't have a direct effect on our body. The human brain is extremely sensitive to sound and music and music activates different areas of the brain which are involved in our cognition, motor function, language, emotions etc. The vibration of the sound from our environment travels through the different parts of the ear in the form of sound waves (such as the outer ear, ear-drum, middle ear, stapes, cochlea and auditory nerve) and finally, through the auditory cortex, small electrical impulses go to the temporal lobe of the brain which illuminates lyrics and sound of music. After the illumination emotional center of the brain's amygdala gets activated and it creates an emotion of fear or pleasure, frontal lobe then decides the emotion of music and parietal lobe analysis the pitches and rhythm. Afterward, the visual cortex of occipital lobe integrates the visual information of the music, later if we are tapping while listening song the cerebellum which is responsible for motor and balance gets activated. Hippocampus stores the memory of the song and reminds musical memory while listening. Later, the hypothalamus which is in charge of regulating chemicals that control our endocrine and nervous systems, releases hormones. And finally, if we like the music and it creates rewarding feeling, then from nucleus accumbens (NAc) one monoamine neurotransmitter called dopamine releases. Dopamine is the hormone for pleasurable feelings, satisfaction and motivation. So, when dopamine releases in the ventral tegmental area (VTA) and travels through various parts of the brain, it makes announcement in our body that the experience was so good, let's do it again in the coming future. This neurotransmitter only releases when we have good food, reproduction and listen to music.^{13,14,15,16} Isn't the human brain so amazing? The story about music doesn't end here, there are other interesting facts as well.

Brain consists of two parts : left hemisphere and right hemisphere. The left hemisphere of brain is associated with our language, comprehension, mathematics and writing skills while creativity, musical abilities, artistic and spatial ability are controlled by the right hemisphere of the brain.^{17,18,19} Music therapy has been proven as having a significant effect in stimulating specific circuits and activates right hemisphere of the brain.^{13&20} Brain imaging technologies have revealed that when we listen to music, the right hemisphere is activated in response to emotional experiences and it has also been reported that imagining music activates the areas on this side.²¹

Music works as an entrainment for regulating blood pressure, heart rate, breathing pattern, sensory and motor function etc. Rhythmic entrainment works when our biological rhythm gets locked by the external musical frequency and rhythm through an auditory rhythmic stimulus. Rhythmic entrainment is used by music therapists for brain rehabilitative training and learning while associating music and rhythm.^{22,23,24}

Several studies have reported that musical training induces structural and functional cerebral neuroplastic processes and it was observed that non-musicians lack structural and functional cerebral characteristics that musicians have, which are generally correlated with the age at which they began musical training.^{25,26} Supportive literature also reported that, musicians brains have a larger anterior

portion of the corpus callosum than non-musicians brain and male musicians are having a higher average relative cerebellar volume in comparison of male non-musician.^{27,28}

In some studies, researchers suggested that listening to Johan Strauss' music increased atrial filling fraction, atrial natriuretic peptide while decreasing cortisol and tissue-type plasminogen activator (t-PA). H. W. Henze's music reduced prolactin, cortisol, noradrenaline and t-PA concentrations^{29,30,31,23}. Music by Ravi Shankar resulted in lower cortisol, noradrenaline and t-PA concentrations. Music has been shown to be as effective as benzodiazepines and 5 hydroxy tryptamine (HT) agonists in combating the negative effects of stress on immunity. It is also proved that music can cause the production of hormones and neurotransmitters that aid in T cell proliferation and antitumor signaling.^{31,33,34} In some studies, authors concluded that music has a greater chance of eliciting musical chills or goosebumps, which can be experienced after listening to music expressing happiness and sadness.^{35,36,37}

In a hospital setting, music therapy as a non-pharmacological intervention can be helpful for the patients to regulate vital signs³⁸, reduce pain^{39,40,41}, reduce length of hospital staying^{42,43}, improve co-operation level⁴⁴, increase patient's satisfaction^{45,46}, reduce their anxiety^{47,48}, stress^{49,50}, depression^{47,51,52} and induce relaxation⁵³ etc.

The journey of a human starts with birth. It has been clinically proven that, if the mother is healthy and happy, the baby will be healthy as well^{54,55}. Music therapy can have a significant influence on the pregnant women in the Obstetrics and Gynecology (OB-GYN) department. In a study, authors tried to assess the effect of live music therapy on pregnant women's heart rates and self-reported anxiety. The study was conducted in Finland among 102 pregnant women with high risk pregnancy and they were divided into a musical group and a control group. Here, music therapists used Lyre as a musical instrument along with it patient's preferred lullaby was hummed. Researchers found that the heart rate variability (HRV) and anxiety of musical group were significantly better than the control group.⁵⁶

In another study which was conducted in Iran, researchers assessed the impact of music on labor pain and progression in the active stage of first labor. Thirty pregnant women were divided into 2 groups based on their willingness. The experimental group listened to soothing music from Manouchehr Cheshmazar's "Barane Eshgh" (Love Rain) through headphones during the first stage of labor and when there were no uterine contractions, the headphones were removed. On the other hand, the control group got standard medications and finally authors discovered a notable difference in pain sensation reduction between the musical and control groups.⁵⁷

There is a large body of research that shows that music therapy can benefit Pediatric patients. In 2013, Loewy Jet al conducted a study among 272 premature infants in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) to assess the impact of music therapy on infant vital signs (heart rate, oxygen saturation level and respiratory rate), sleep and feeding behavior. The authors discovered that live sound, entrained breath sound and parents-preferred lullabies had an effect on cardiac, respiratory, feeding and sucking patterns. Researchers also found that parents preferred lullabies can enhance infant-parent bonding.⁵⁸

Music therapy in NICU can also be helpful to reduce pain perception, achieve weight gain, reduce the length of hospital staying.^{59,60} Music therapy might also have a significant effect on children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), learning and development disorder, mood

disorders, chronic/acute physical illness.^{61,62,63}

Neurologic music therapy (NMT) has a significant effect on neurological rehabilitation for patients with coma, stroke, aphasia, parkinson's disease, dementia, alzheimer's disease and other conditions^{64,65,66,67,68}. In a study, Golino AJ et al tried to assess the impact of active music therapy interventions on physiological parameters as well as patients' self-reported pain and anxiety levels in the intensive care unit (ICU). For 30 minutes, 52 patients received either a relaxation intervention/guided imagery or preferred music listening. Researchers found a significant decrease in the patient's respiratory rate, heart rate, self-reported pain and anxiety. There was no significant measure of oxygen saturation.⁶⁹

In another study, authors found that rhythmic auditory stimulation (RAS) might have a great impact on the gait training of stroke patients.⁷⁰

There are several pieces of supportive literature where it has been declared that music therapy has an impact on patients with cardiovascular diseases. Music therapy can be helpful to reduce the anxiety and stress of coronary heart disease (CHD) patients⁷¹. Music therapy as procedural support can be effective to reduce the anxiety of patients undergoing coronary angiographic procedures. In a study, researchers divided 94 patients into 3 groups : focused music, loudspeaker music and control group. Authors figured that anxiety levels were significantly lower in both music groups when compared to the control group, but the focused music group had a significantly more positive impression of the sound environment⁷².

Music therapy has been shown to reduce pain perception and anxiety in patients undergoing cataract surgery and intravitreal injections in the ophthalmology department^{73,74}. In one study, 243 patients undergoing cataract surgery were divided into two groups : music and control. The music group was given 20 minutes to listen to their preferred song. It was discovered that the music group's anxiety and pain perception was significantly lower than that of the control group.⁷³

Music therapy techniques might have a remarkable impact on the patients having pulmonary diseases. Canga B. et al reported that music therapy techniques like music visualization, wind instrument playing and singing combined with pulmonary rehabilitation may benefit patients with chronic pulmonary diseases (COPD) suffering from depression, dyspnea, and fatigue⁷⁵.

Another study found that music therapy techniques such as playing a wind or brass instruments, singing and vocal-assisted breathing exercises could significantly reduce asthma symptoms in patients.⁷⁶

Throughout dental procedures, music therapy can help patients to regulate their heart rate and blood pressure, as well as reduce their pain perception and anxiety^{77,78,79}. There are some evidences that music therapy may have an impact on pain perception, anxiety and the need for anesthesia in ear-nose-throat (ENT) patients undergoing various surgeries and procedures.^{80,81}

Music is something that connects our emotions, motivation and behavior, at the same time induces relaxation. Music therapy as an inter-disciplinary medicine may have a significant impact on psychiatry patients suffering from various mental health disorders^{82,83}. Music therapy combined with treatment as usual (TAU) was found to be more significant than music therapy alone or TAU alone in a review article. Authors also discovered that music therapy could help depressed people to reduce their anxiety and improve their functioning⁵¹. Another research showed that combining music therapy

with cognitive behavioral therapy can help adolescents to reduce their social anxiety.⁸⁴

In 2017, Geretsegger M. et al suggested that music therapy as an additional treatment can improve the global state, social functioning and quality of life of patients with schizophrenia and schizophrenia-like disorders.⁸⁵

Music therapy as complementary medicine can help cancer patients to improve their physical and psychological health. It can also help to reduce their pain perception, anxiety, chemotherapy side effects, relaxation induction and mood disturbance^{86,87,88,89,90,91}. In one study, breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy were divided into two groups : music and control. Prior to chemotherapy, the music group received a 30-minute musical intervention. As a result, the music group had a higher quality of life than the control group and reduction of depression, anxiety and vomiting incidences were also found.⁹²

Recently, when the entire world was terrified by the sudden outbreak of covid-19 and millions of people were died, music therapists were working to support the mental health of coronavirus patients. Hasina et al reported that music therapy interventions reduced anxiety and improved quality of life in COVID-19 patients.⁹³

Music therapy as a non-pharmacological treatment has been shown to improve physiological and psychological health with no negative side effects. It is extremely beneficial in terms of cognitive functioning, motor functioning, emotional expression, communication, self-esteem and overall quality of life. Music therapy connects a person's mind and body assists the individual in achieving a positive mood effect, which gradually leads to physical and mental well-being^{13-16, 20-24, 64-69,94}. This review article suggests for the systematic review and meta-analysis of the effect of music therapy in hospital settings in future and firmly believe that trained and clinically practiced music therapists can collaborate with other health professionals in the hospital settings to address patients' physical and psychological wellness. Every hospital, clinic, rehabilitation center and educational institution should have music therapist so that the overall well-being can be achieved.

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